

Spectral Evidence of Spatial Context Variation Surrounding NBS Interventions in Diverse Urban Environments

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Abstract: Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are widely implemented to enhance urban resilience, however, their performance is strongly influenced by spatial environments in which they are embedded. This study examines how surrounding urban context shapes the ecological functioning potential of three European NBS interventions: Linderud Garden (Oslo), Giardino Nascosto (Milan), and Lucavsala Community Garden (Riga). Using Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery acquired during the peak summer season, three spectral indices, NDVI, NDMI, and NDBI were calculated within 100 m, 300 m, and 500 m buffers to characterize vegetation greenness, moisture availability, and built-up intensity. Results reveal distinct contextual patterns as Lucavsala Community Garden (Riga) is embedded in a highly supportive landscape, reflected in higher NDVI and NDMI values and strongly negative NDBI, indicating abundant vegetation and limited urban pressure. Linderud Garden (Oslo) exhibits a moderately supportive context, with greener and moister micro-surroundings transitioning into more urbanized conditions at larger distances. In contrast, Giardino Nascosto (Milan) is situated within a dense and comparatively dry urban fabric, characterized by lower NDVI, declining NDMI, and positive NDBI values. These findings demonstrate that NBS potential is co-determined by broader spatial structure rather than site characteristics only, underscoring the importance of integrating spatial diagnostics into context-sensitive urban resilience planning.

Keywords: nature-based solutions; spatial context; remote sensing; spectral indices (NDVI, NDMI, NDBI).

1 Introduction

Urban areas across Europe are increasingly turning to Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) to address climate change, biodiversity loss, and declining environmental quality (Fang et al. 2024). While interventions such as community gardens, urban parks, rain gardens, and green corridors are widely promoted for their ecological and social benefits, their performance is not determined by design alone (Sowińska-Świerkosz and García 2021). The spatial context in which NBS are embedded, shaped by surrounding land-use patterns, vegetation structure, and built-up intensity, plays a decisive role in their ecological potential, resilience, and long-term sustainability (Atanasova et al. 2021, Biątek and Łagód 2025).

Remote sensing offers effective means to characterize these contextual conditions (Abate et al. 2025). Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery enables the quantification of

vegetation greenness, moisture availability, and built-up pressure at multiple spatial scales. Spectral indices such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), and Normalized Difference Built-Up Index (NDBI) provide consistent indicators of ecological support or urban stress around NBS sites (Ricotta et al. 1999, Zha et al. 2003, Jin and Sader 2005). Applying these indices across buffer zones enables a wider understanding of how micro and macro-scale conditions influence NBS functioning.

This study focuses on three NBS interventions within the NatureScape project Transformation Labs (T-Labs) located in Oslo (Norway), Riga (Latvia), and Milan (Italy), each embedded in contrasting urban fabrics. By analyzing NDVI, NDMI, and NDBI within 100 m, 300 m, and 500 m buffers, the research evaluates how differences in greenness, moisture, and built-up intensity reflect varying levels of ecological support. Understanding these contextual variations is essential for assessing NBS performance and informing planning strategies that integrate nature more effectively into complex urban systems.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area Descriptions

The study examines three NBS interventions located in contrasting European urban settings: Linderud Garden in Oslo, Lucavsala Community Garden in Riga and Giardino Nascosto in Milan (see Figure 1a, 1b and 1c) respectively. Oslo represents a mixed residential landscape with moderate greenness and semi-natural vegetation. Milan is embedded in a dense, impervious Mediterranean urban core with limited ecological connectivity. Riga, by contrast, is situated in a riverine, highly vegetated, low-pressure environment, offering a strongly supportive ecological context for NBS functioning.

2.2 Data Collection and Processing

Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery was used as the primary data source because its 10 -20m spatial resolution, frequent revisit cycle, and open access make it well suited for urban ecological assessments. Sentinel-2 Level-1C imagery with less than 5% cloud cover obtained from June 2025 were selected to ensure consistent seasonal conditions. The imagery acquired was captured on 13-06-2025 for Oslo NBS site, 15-06-2025 for Riga NBS site, and 14-06-2025 for Milan NBS site, providing comparable

peak summer vegetation and moisture conditions across sites.

Figure 1. Satellite imagery of study areas in a) Oslo, b) Riga, and c) Milan sites.

The imagery was imported into ArcGIS Pro for preprocessing, including clipping to each study area and its corresponding buffer zones. Circular buffers of 100 m, 300 m, and 500 m were generated around each NBS site to represent micro-, meso-, and macro-scale zones within the nearby surroundings of the interventions, allowing assessment of how vegetation, moisture, and built-up intensity vary with distance. The datasets were thereafter used for calculating spectral indices and subsequent zonal statistics.

Majorly three spectral indices were computed due to their relevance for assessing ecological support and urban pressure.

- Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

NDVI quantifies vegetation greenness and photosynthetic activity (Ricotta et al. 1999). NDVI calculated based on the Sentinel 2 bands is shown in equation (1) below.

$$NDVI = \frac{B_8 - B_4}{B_8 + B_4} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. Buffered NDVI Spectral Maps of (a) Oslo NBS Site, (b) Riga NBS Site, (c) Milan NBS Site.

Figure 3. Buffered NDMI Spectral Maps of (a) Oslo NBS Site, (b) Riga NBS Site, (c) Milan NBS Site.

where: Band 8 (B_8) = Near Infrared (NIR), Band 4 (B_4) = Red.

- Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI)

NDMI measures vegetation moisture content and soil wetness (Jin and Sader 2005). NDMI calculated based on the Sentinel 2 bands is shown in equation (2) below.

$$NDMI = \frac{B_8 - B_{11}}{B_8 + B_{11}} \quad (2)$$

where: Band 8 (B_8) = Near Infrared (NIR), Band 11 (B_{11}) = Shortwave Infrared (SWIR).

- Normalized Difference Built-Up Index (NDBI)

NDBI highlights built-up surfaces and imperviousness (Zha et al. 2003). NDBI calculated based on the Sentinel 2 bands is shown in equation (3) below.

$$NDMI = \frac{B_{11} - B_8}{B_{11} + B_8} \quad (3)$$

where: Band 8 (B_8) = Near Infrared (NIR), Band 11 (B_{11}) = Shortwave Infrared (SWIR).

3 Results

The spectral index statistics provided a clear foundation for interpreting how greenness, moisture, and built-up intensity vary around the three NBS sites. The mean NDVI, NDMI, and NDBI values across the 100 m, 300 m, and 500 m buffers illustrate distinct environmental gradients that differentiate supportive, mixed, and constrained spatial contexts, as seen in Table 1. To complement the numerical results, the spatial distribution of these indices was also visualised through buffer-based spectral maps for Oslo, Riga, and Milan as seen in Figure 2, 3 and 4. These spectral maps illustrate how vegetation cover, moisture patterns, and built-up surfaces are arranged around each NBS site, revealing spatial heterogeneity that cannot only be captured by summary statistics table.

Figure 4. Buffered NDBI Spectral Maps of (a) Oslo NBS Site, (b) Riga NBS Site, (c) Milan NBS Site.

Table 1. Spatial Context Metrics Derived from Spectral Indices.

NBS Intervention	Spectral Indices	Buffer Zone	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Mean	Standard Deviation
Linderud Community Garden (Oslo)	NDVI	100 m	0.08	0.60	0.52	0.43	0.12
		300 m	-0.03	0.60	0.62	0.29	0.15
		500 m	-0.03	0.60	0.62	0.28	0.14
	NDMI	100 m	-0.17	0.37	0.54	0.20	0.11
		300 m	-0.17	0.37	0.54	0.12	0.11
		500 m	-0.17	0.37	0.54	0.12	0.09
	NDBI	100 m	-0.37	0.17	0.54	-0.20	0.11
		300 m	-0.37	0.17	0.54	-0.12	0.11
		500 m	-0.37	0.17	0.54	-0.12	0.09
Lucavsala Community Garden (Riga)	NDVI	100 m	0.30	0.56	0.26	0.48	0.05
		300 m	0.09	0.61	0.53	0.44	0.08
		500 m	-0.01	0.61	0.62	0.37	0.15
	NDMI	100 m	0.10	0.33	0.24	0.23	0.05
		300 m	-0.09	0.37	0.46	0.20	0.08
		500 m	-0.14	0.37	0.51	0.17	0.09
	NDBI	100 m	-0.33	-0.10	0.24	-0.23	0.05
		300 m	-0.37	0.09	0.46	-0.20	0.08
		500 m	-0.37	0.14	0.51	-0.17	0.09
Giardino Nascosto Garden (Milan)	NDVI	100 m	0.04	0.41	0.37	0.20	0.10
		300 m	0.01	0.41	0.40	0.13	0.09
		500 m	0.01	0.41	0.40	0.12	0.08
	NDMI	100 m	-0.12	0.22	0.34	0.05	0.08
		300 m	-0.18	0.22	0.40	0.00	0.08
		500 m	-0.21	0.22	0.43	-0.01	0.08
	NDBI	100 m	-0.22	0.12	0.34	-0.05	0.08
		300 m	-0.22	0.18	0.40	0.00	0.08
		500 m	-0.22	0.21	0.43	0.01	0.08

4 Discussion

The spectral analysis reveals how surrounding urban fabric fundamentally shapes NBS ecological potential through distinct environmental gradients and these patterns indicate functional differences in ecosystem service delivery capacity. For the case of vegetation connectivity and ecological support, Riga’s NBS site (Lucavsala community garden) consistently high NDVI across all buffers (0.48–0.37) suggests strong ecological connectivity that can facilitate pollinator movement, seed dispersal, and microclimate regulation beyond the immediate

intervention (Atanasova et al. 2021). This aligns with findings by (Sowińska-Świerkosz and García 2021) that NBS performance depends critically on landscape-scale green infrastructure networks. Conversely, Milan's NBS site sharp NDVI decline (0.20 - 0.12) indicates functional isolation, where ecosystem services remain spatially constrained and vulnerable to edge effects from the surrounding built environment (Biatek and Łagód 2025). The moderate gradient in Oslo site (0.43 - 0.28) represents a transitional context where NBS benefits may extend into semi-natural residential areas but weaken in more urbanized zones.

On the side of hydrological implications of moisture patterns, the NDMI values directly relate to vegetation water stress and evapotranspiration capacity. Lucavsala community garden (Riga) positive NDMI (0.230 - 0.171) indicates sustained moisture availability that supports drought resilience and cooling through evapotranspiration, which is a critical function during heat events (Fang et al. 2024). Milan's NBS site shift from marginal moisture (0.054) to negative values (- 0.014) at 500 m suggests limited hydrological buffering capacity, potentially constraining stormwater retention and urban heat mitigation effectiveness. This moisture deficit tends to explain why Mediterranean NBS interventions often underperform relative to temperate counterparts despite similar design approaches.

Additionally, for the case of built-up intensity, the transition from negative to positive NDBI in Milan NBS site (- 0.057 to 0.014) marks a critical threshold where impervious surfaces dominate, fragmenting habitat networks and intensifying urban heat island effects. This contrasts sharply with Riga's NBS site consistently negative NDBI (- 0.230 to - 0.171), indicating minimal urban pressure across scales. These patterns suggest that effective NBS planning requires not only site-level interventions but strategic integration with broader green infrastructure to overcome contextual constraints (Atanasova et al. 2021). Understanding these multi-scale environmental gradients enables context-sensitive NBS design that accounts for spatial opportunities and limitations inherent to diverse urban fabrics.

5 Conclusions

The findings demonstrate that NBS ecological potential is co-determined by surrounding spatial context. While Riga NBS site exhibits optimal performance metrics (high greenness, strong moisture availability, and minimal urban pressure), this supportive setting paradoxically indicates lower intervention urgency. Conversely, Milan's NBS site constrained context (dense fabric, moisture deficit, positive NDBI) signals greatest ecological stress, precisely where NBS interventions are most critically needed to mitigate urban heat and improve thermal comfort. Oslo represents an intermediate scenario with moderate support that could facilitate ecosystem service delivery. These spectral patterns reveal a fundamental planning tension as ecologically optimal conditions for NBS functioning may not align with locations of greatest societal need. Context-sensitive design should therefore balance ecological constraints against intervention priority to maximize urban resilience benefits where community members face the most severe environmental pressures.

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6 References

- Abate, N., Ronchi, D., Zaia, S. E., Ciccone, G., Frisetti, A., Sileo, M., ... Pucci, M., 2025. Multi-Resolution and Multi-Temporal Satellite Remote Sensing Analysis to Understand Human-Induced Changes in the Landscape for the Protection of Cultural Heritage: The Case Study of the MapDam Project, Syria. *Land*, 14(11), 2233.
- Atanasova, N., Castellar, J. A., Pineda-Martos, R., Nika, C. E., Katsou, E., Istenič, D., ... Langergraber, G., 2021. Nature-based solutions and circularity in cities. *Circular Economy and Sustainability*, 1(1), 319-332.
- Białek, A., Łagód, G., 2025. The impact of physical-geographical conditions on the sizing of rain gardens: A spatial case of Poland. *Journal of Ecological Engineering* 26: 460–476.
- Fang, X., Li, J., Ma, Q., Zhou, R., Du, S., 2024. A quantitative review of nature-based solutions for urban sustainability (2016–2022): From science to implementation. *Science of the Total Environment*, 927, 172219.
- Jin, S., Sader, S. A., 2005. Comparison of time series tasseled cap wetness and the normalized difference moisture index in detecting forest disturbances. *Remote sensing of Environment*, 94(3), 364-372.
- Ricotta, C., Avena, G., De Palma, A., 1999. Mapping and monitoring net primary productivity with AVHRR NDVI time-series: statistical equivalence of cumulative vegetation indices. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 54(5-6), 325-331.
- Sowińska-Świerkosz, B., García, J., 2021. A new evaluation framework for nature-based solutions (NBS) projects based on the application of performance questions and indicators approach. *Science of The Total Environment* 787: 147615.
- Zha, Y., Gao, J., Ni, S., 2003. Use of normalized difference built-up index in automatically mapping urban areas from TM imagery. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 24. Taylor & Francis: 583–594.